

A new dicephalic *Lampropeltis t. triangulum* from Maine, USA

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INTRODUCTION

Lampropeltis t. triangulum (Lacépède, 1788), the common Milk Snake, inhabits northeastern USA and southeastern Canada. It occurs in southern Maine, ranging as far north as 44°50'N in Phillips County (HUNTER et al., 1999). More than 600 legitimate records exist documenting 143 species of snakes (in 75 genera from eight families) in which two-headedness or dicephalism has occurred (WALLACH, 2004).

COMMON MILK SNAKE

Six previous records of dicephalism are known in *Lampropeltis t. triangulum*. BANCROFT (1769: 214-215) reported and illustrated a specimen from Lake Champlain, New York that represented the first record of dicephalism in the New World (SMITH & CHISZAR, 1988). SMITH (1882: 690) recorded a specimen from Ingham County, Michigan, and HOWEY (1883: 161) mentioned a specimen from Fayetteville, Arkansas. JOHNSON (1902: 528) described a specimen collected near the New York Zoological Park.

The dicephalic hatchling *Lampropeltis t. triangulum* in its habitat.

Photo: J. Tricarico

BLATCHLEY (1906: 421) reported a specimen from Terre Haute, Indiana. And DITMARS (1970: 345) mentioned a half grown specimen from the Bronx, New York. ERNST (1960: 5) reported a specimen from Columbia, Pennsylvania. The present dicephalic hatchling was collected on 26 September 2004 near Winthrop, Maine (ca. 44°18'N, 70°00'W) by Glen and Jan

Tricarico. The location is quite near the northernmost limit of the species in Maine. Glen Tricarico found the specimen beneath a stone in a rock wall at 5:00 p.m. It shed one week later on 7 October. Since it had not fed and the shed could only have been the post-hatching moult, it presumably was newborn and probably hatched in late September. Most *Lampropeltis triangulum* hatch in August or September (ERNST & ERNST, 2003). Jan Tricarico, knowing the rarity and value of two-headed snakes, donated it to the Avian Haven Wild Bird Rehabilitation Center in Palermo, Maine, with instructions to find a good home for it. Marc Payne of Avian Haven eventually discovered my interest in dicephalic snakes and located me for the donation.

It is not known what causes dicephalism but the most logical scenario is that a single embryo partially divides during the earliest stages of development. Such abnormalities could possibly be induced by extremes in temperature (both high and low) during incubation, inbreeding in captive individuals, and chemical or environmental pollution.

The only case known of reproduction by a dicephalic snake is a clutch of fifteen eggs laid by Thelma & Louise, a female

The two-headed snake *Lampropeltis t. triangulum* with finger for size comparison.

Photo: J. Tricarico

dicephalic *Lampropeltis getula californiae* that lived at the San Diego Zoo until 2000. All fifteen neonates were perfectly formed with a single head, suggesting that dicephalism is a developmental or environmental problem rather than a genetic inheritable trait.

BEHAVIOUR

The snake was named Brady & Belichick (or B & B) after the New England Patriots football team quarterback and coach, the left head being Brady and the right head Belichick. B & B weighed 4.0 g and measured 200 mm in total length upon arrival. After refusing to eat various invertebrates (earthworms, snails, slugs, crickets, mealworms, and mouse tails and limbs), I obtained two *Scincella lateralis* from Jeff Boundy in Louisiana on 5 November 2004. Immediately after placing the smallest skink in the container with B & B, the snake started thrashing around. Upon closer inspection, I discovered that the right head (Belichick) had attacked the left head (Brady) and was chewing on it. I separated the heads and placed the lizard's head in Brady's mouth. Brady grabbed the skink and began swallowing it, but Belichick kept trying to eat the lizard also so I had to place a card between the two heads. This quieted Belichick down. Brady kept chewing and chewing but was unsuccessful in swallowing the lizard so I cut it in half and gave the posterior half to Belichick, who immediately started to eat it. Both heads were content to swallow simultaneously but I was concerned that the two food items would meet and get stuck at the junction of the oesophagi. Belichick seemed to be a better feeder: his jaw movements were faster than Brady's and he effectively swallowed his half before Brady did. Eventually both heads swallowed their meals, demonstrat-

Dorsal view of the dicephalic hatchling *Lampropeltis t. triangulum*.

Photo: J. Woodward

ing that both heads had complete connections to the stomach (sometimes one head is vestigial and cannot eat). I also placed a mouse leg in each mouth when the lizard was disappearing down the gullet and both heads continued to eat.

It first appeared that the Belichick's head would be dominant over Brady's. However, subsequent feedings have demonstrated that both heads eat on their own but Belichick swallows faster.

For the second meal, on 8 November, I offered two pinkies that were scented with the remaining skink. Both heads started eating a pinkie but Belichick completely swallowed his mouse before Brady even got his head swallowed. Then Belichick evi-

dently lost interest and started crawling around the cage, dragging Brady along with a half-swallowed mouse. After trying to swallow for 20 minutes, Brady gave up and spit the pinkie out as it could not get a good grip. The smallest pinkie mice were very difficult to swallow because they were 3-4 times the size of the snake's heads.

For the third meal on 11 November, I offered a pinkie only to Belichick, and while Belichick took the mouse and started swallowing it, Brady kept crawling around and dragging Belichick backwards. Eventually Belichick gave up and spit out the mouse, after which neither head would start feeding again (on pinkie, skink, or mouse legs).

On 15 November, I tried feeding again but neither head would take a pinkie or the skink. I left a pinkie in the cage and several hours later it was gone. One head had eaten it by itself. On 17 November, it shed for the second time; it was 210 mm long and weighed 4.7 g. It then started eating single pinkies regularly (about every 5 days), alternating between Brady and Be-

lichick. All recorded observations of which head fed are as follows: Brady & Belichick, Belichick, Belichick, Brady, Brady, Belichick, Belichick, Brady, Belichick, Brady, Belichick, Belichick, Brady, Belichick, and Belichick. That is the right head 9 times, the left head 5 times, both heads once, and 4 times when feeding was not observed. Belichick seems to feed about twice as often as Brady so the right head may be dominant. For further data on growth, see table on the next page.

DISCUSSION

The two heads have demonstrated an ability to learn. First, they learned not to fight one another for food, that it ended up in the stomach no matter which head fed. Then it learned that one head should be still while the other fed or nothing would get eaten. Therefore, the snake, although it has two separate and independent brains, has learned to cooperate. It is apparent at times that each head wants to crawl in a different

Dorsal view of the dicephalic hatchling *Lampropeltis t. triangulum*.

Photo: J. Woodward

direction and is sending conflicting signals to the body musculature as both heads and the necks will vibrate rapidly for a second or two. Then the snake becomes still and crawls off in a certain direction. It is almost as if each head is fighting for control. At other times the snake will make a smooth transition from quiescence to locomotor motion. The snake can crawl with both heads parallel to one another, both heads angled away from each other, or one head lying on top of the other (when it seems to crawl in the straightest manner). Sometimes Brady will lie on top of Belichick while crawling; at other times Belichick will lie on top of Brady.

POSTSCRIPT

I continue to study dicephalic snakes and am quite interested in contacting anyone who has unpublished information on any living or dead specimen, whether it is a personal observation, news article, photo, or actual specimen. My eventual goal is to produce a book that chronicles all records of dicephalic snakes.

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Shed #	Date	Weight (g)	Length (mm)
1	26 Sept 2004	ca.4.0	ca. 200
2	17 Nov 2004	4.7	210
3	29 Dec 2004	5.5	220
4	20 Feb 2005	6.4	230
5	4 May 2005	7.7	240
6	11 June 2005	8.1	260

Table: Data on moults and growth.

SUMMARY

A recently hatched dicephalic *Lampropeltis triangulum* was found in the wild in September 2004. Observations on feeding, growth, and locomotory behaviour are reported for the first nine months of its life.

SAMENVATTING

In september 2004 werd een pas geboren tweekoppige *Lampropeltis triangulum* in het wild gevonden. Hier wordt verslag gedaan van waarnemingen over voeding, groei en voortbeweging zoals deze gedurende de eerste negen maanden van het leven van het dier verricht zijn.